

DEPTH PROFILING OF IMPLANTED DEUTERIUM IN LUNAR-ANALOG SILICATES USING NRA AND KEV TOF-SIMS. A. Košir¹, J. Simčič¹, S. Markelj¹, A. Peschel², M. Vrabec³, T. Sotelšek³, J. Medved⁴, J. M. Neumann⁵, J. Kovač⁶, T. Filipič⁶ and M. Čekada⁷, ¹ Jožef Stefan Institute, Low and Medium Energy Physics Dept., Ljubljana, Slovenia, ² Technical University Munich, Professorship for Lunar and Planetary Exploration, Munich, Germany, ³ University of Ljubljana, Faculty of Natural Sciences and Engineering, Dept. of Geology, Ljubljana, Slovenia. ⁴ University of Ljubljana, Faculty of Natural Sciences and Engineering, Dept. of Materials and Metallurgy, Ljubljana, Slovenia. ⁵ University of Ljubljana, Faculty of Mathematics and Physics, Dept. of Physics, Ljubljana, Slovenia, ⁶ Jožef Stefan Institute, Dept. of Surface Engineering, Ljubljana, Slovenia, ⁷ Jožef Stefan Institute, Dept. of Thin Films and Surfaces, Ljubljana, Slovenia

Introduction: The lunar surface is continuously exposed to the solar wind, leading to hydrogen implantation in lunar minerals and glasses - a process first proposed in the 1970s and supported by numerous subsequent studies showing that implanted protons can form hydroxyl and related water-group species [1-4]. Recent nanoscale and spectroscopic investigations of impact glass beads returned by the Chang'e-5 mission further demonstrate that solar-wind-derived hydrogen can form and be temporarily retained as OH/H₂O within glassy materials before being released during thermal cycling [5,6]. To quantify the implantation, retention, and release behavior of solar-wind-analog hydrogen under controlled conditions, we investigated an olivine crystal and a synthetic lunar-like glass, enabling direct comparison of implantation profiles and hydrogen stability in materials relevant to the uppermost lunar regolith.

Olivine is a commonly used analogue for lunar materials. The glass analogue was synthesized from oxide powders representing average Mare and Highlands compositions [5]. The mixture was homogenized, consolidated into pellets, melted under vacuum in an induction furnace, and rapidly quenched in a liquid-nitrogen-cooled copper mold. Analysis using optical microscopy, X-ray diffraction, and Scanning Electron Microscopy with Energy Dispersive Spectroscopy (SEM-EDS) confirmed a predominantly amorphous structure with minor iron inclusions formed during melting.

Experiments: Both samples were irradiated with deuterium ions at ~1 keV to simulate the implantation range characteristic of solar-wind ions. Deuterium was selected to distinguish newly formed water-group species (OD/D₂O) from any pre-existing hydrogen components (e.g., OH/H₂O).

Near-surface deuterium distributions were measured using Nuclear Reaction Analysis (NRA) with a ³He beam at different energies ranging from 0.7 MeV to 4.2 MeV. Reaction products and backscattered ions were detected using two PIPS detectors in the INSIBA chamber [7,8]. The samples were heated to ~375 °C and allowed to cool naturally, after which a follow-up NRA measurement quantified the retained implanted inventory. Depth profiles derived through SIMNRA fitting [9] show implanted regions confined

to the upper few hundred nanometers, with peak concentrations of ~10% for olivine and ~12% for the glass analogue. Heating resulted in ~40% deuterium loss from both samples without evidence of deeper diffusion.

High-sensitivity depth profiles were obtained using kilo-electronvolt Time-of-Flight Secondary Ion Mass Spectroscopy (keV ToF-SIMS) with a 2 keV Cs⁺ sputter beam and a 30 keV Bi⁺ analytical beam. Crater depths, initially unknown, were determined using confocal-laser profilometry. The resulting profiles reveal broader D-related features in olivine and a more confined distribution in the glass. Normalized ion-signal ratios, (m/z=2)/(m/z=1) and (m/z=18)/(m/z=17), confirm the implanted-deuterium origin of these features.

Discussion: Compared to the NRA profiles, the keV ToF-SIMS data show broader and deeper deuterium-related signals in olivine, while the glass remains more consistent with NRA results. We attribute these differences primarily to unequal storage intervals between implantation and keV ToF-SIMS analysis (approximately 2 months for the glass vs. 7 months for the olivine). Additional factors include insufficient surface polishing (affecting depth calibration), storage outside vacuum, charging during analysis, and the lack of a dedicated ToF-SIMS calibration standard.

Conclusion: Our results demonstrate that solar-wind-analog deuterium is implanted only within the upper few hundred nanometers of both olivine and synthetic lunar-like glass, reaching peak concentrations of ~10-12 at.%. The thermal desorption measurements show that heating removes implanted deuterium predominantly from the near-surface region, while no evidence of diffusion deeper into the material is observed. Discrepancies between NRA and keV ToF-SIMS profiles emphasize the necessity for improved surface preparation, calibration, and analytical methods to reduce systematic errors in future studies.

References: [1] Liu Y. et al., *Nat. Geosci.* 5 (2012) 779-782. [2] Bradley J. P. et al., *PNAS* 111 (2014) 1732-1735. [3] Farrell W. M. et al., *Icarus* 255 (2015) 116-126. [4] Jones B. M. et al., *Geophys. Res. Lett.* 45 (2018) 10959-10967. [5] He H. et al., *Nat. Geosci.* 16

(2023) 294-300. [6] Xu Y. et al., PNAS 119 (2022) e2214395119. [7] Calligaro T. et al., Compr. Anal. Chem. 42 (2004) 227-276. [8] Markelj S. et al., J. Nucl. Mater. 469 (2016) 133-144. [9] Mayer M., AIP Conf. Proc. 475 (1999) 541-544.